

COMPUTER-ASSISTED SOUNDING SELECTION FOR THE SHIPBOARD DATA SYSTEM III

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ABSTRACT

Shipboard Data System III (SDS III) is being developed to replace the existing hydrographic data acquisition and processing systems. An automated selection of significant depths was developed to replace the present manual procedure in order to reduce the processing time. The accuracy of this selection process has been tested and evaluated with respect to the present manual technique.

1. INTRODUCTION

The National Ocean Service (NOS) is developing a new hydrographic data acquisition and data processing system to replace the aging HYDROPLOT system. The Shipboard Data System III (SDS III) will consist of two major subsystems, the Data Acquisition System (DAS) and the Data Processing System (DPS). The procurement of the hardware for both systems has been executed with the delivery of the first production systems planned for 1986. The development of the software is in progress with an Operational Capabilities Demonstration planned for 1987.

The processing of raw sounding data is one area where the greater capability of the DPS will improve efficiency. Current HYDROPLOT practice requires the manual addition of significant depth data to the fixed time sounding interval data that is automatically recorded. The primary goal of the total DPS sounding data processing scheme is to improve processing efficiency, while keeping current general procedures. The approach is to assist the hydrographer by providing fast, interactive tools while not sacrificing his/her control of the data flow. The following are also desirable goals:

- * An automated peak and deep selection technique that would pick at least the same additional soundings that the hydrographer would select.
- * A selection routine that would be effective in all geographic areas surveyed by NOS.
- * A standardized sounding selection process.
- * A more accurate digital bottom profile representation.

The development of the complete DPS sounding processing scheme assumed the following constraints or procedures:

- * The DAS would record ALL soundings. The present DSF-6000N echo sounder can digitize 100,000 narrow-beam and wide-beam soundings in 6 hours of launch acquisition time.
- * The DAS would record the time at which fixed-interval soundings would be retained. These selections would be sufficient to meet the sounding interval at the survey scale.
- * The verification module would contain a two-dimensional excessing routine to select the most significant sounding in a plottable area.

2. GENERAL APPROACH

The SDS III sounding selection process picks retained depths from a large volume of raw soundings in four steps. These are (1) retrieving and preparing the raw sounding data, (2) automatic marking of the additional significant peaks or deeps, (3) storing the marked sounding data, and (4) reviewing and correcting the automatic selections by the hydrographer. The DAS will have established the times that

soundings have to be retained in order to meet the sounding interval requirement. Soundings at these times will always be retained and would represent the minimum number of depths required for the survey.

The subject of this paper is step 2, the automatic selection algorithm. This step first reviews the data set and then marks significant peaks or deeps within each sounding interval. Either the raw data or an alternate bottom simulation can be used as the basis of the additional peak and deep selection.

The automated selection algorithm is a threshold based, point elimination scheme that operates over each sounding interval sequentially. An upper and lower threshold are generated parallel to a bottom segment connecting two soundings that have been established by the DAS as defining the required sounding interval. The width of these thresholds is calculated for each sounding interval and is a function of (1) depth, (2) operator adjustment and (3) a slope correction factor. The purpose of the depth dependency is to reduce selections in deep water as less bottom definition is required for charting purposes. The number of selections made along a sounding line can be partially changed by a sensitivity control. This is the only operator input to adjust for bottom irregularity or for effects of significant vessel heave. The slope correction is used to adjust the threshold window to compensate for the apparent slope angle of the connecting line segment. Its purpose is to reduce selections of insignificant soundings between the most significant peak and subsequent deep. This correction does not suppress the selection of shoulders or minor peaks along steep bottom slopes. The automatic threshold expansion is demonstrated in figure 1.

A particular sounding will be selected as significant if either of two possible criteria is met:

- * It is the one peak or deep outside either threshold, with the greatest vertical distance above or below the line segment connecting the initial sounding selections that define the sounding interval.

OR

- * It is the one peak inside the upper threshold that is shallower than BOTH of the initial sounding selections.

These two criteria are demonstrated in figure 2. Only one peak and one deep may be selected at one time. If a peak or a deep or both are found within the sounding

Figure 1. Automatic expansion of the upper threshold.

interval, the algorithm is applied to each subinterval formed by these additions and the initial selections. This second pass may make additional selection(s) that will more accurately represent the actual bottom profile. Only two passes are permitted. The number of additional selections per sounding interval is thus limited to a maximum of eight.

The selection process is biased toward shoal selection by virtue of the second selection criteria and the lower threshold being twice the width of the upper threshold. This shoal bias was deemed prudent for conservative nautical charting.

3. PERFORMANCE

The performance of the selection process was tested using several data sets. Mathematically derived curves, 912 discrete data points obtained from a DSF-6000N echogram of Lake Union, Washington, and continuously recorded DSF-6000N soundings from the Solomons, Maryland, area of the Chesapeake Bay were used during algorithm development. The latter data set had a few missed depths embedded in it and only these depths were adjusted prior to use. A simple linear interpolation method was used to fill in the missed data. This action is similar to that anticipated by a gap filling or filtering process prior to the selection routine. Parameters chosen as baseline values for testing were:

Figure 2. Examples of selections based on each selection criteria.

- * The baseline sounding interval size was 100 soundings per fixed interval.
- * The baseline selection sensitivity was chosen to be 0.5. This is the greatest sensitivity expected to be used during surveying and results in the largest number of selections.
- * The raw DSF-6000N sounded depths were used as recorded. The selection response of the algorithm was tested for its sensitivity to the four operating

parameters; (1) operator adjustment, (2) sounded depth, (3) sounding interval size, and (4) phase shift. Figures 3 to 6 are used to demonstrate the actual selections within the baseline data set. Each parameter variation being demonstrated by a figure is offset by a fixed 10-foot or 20-foot increment for clarity.

The only operator control over the selection process is the Sensitivity value. This control is intended to reduce the number of selections when the magnitude of echogram sea action (vessel heave) is large or the bottom is highly irregular. The Sensitivity value required for different conditions will be empirically determined after the low-pass filtering and smoothing processes have been completely implemented. The selection response for five Sensitivity values were compared. These results are summarized in table 1 and demonstrated by figure 3. It is noted that values of 1.0, 2.0 and 5.0 are expected to be "normal" values. A value of 10.0 is thought to be an extreme, for use in deep water and rough seas conditions only.

The number of additional selections ranged from 7 to 26 over the testing interval when the Sensitivity was changed. The important result is that although the number of selections is reduced, the basic shape of the bottom profile was not significantly changed at the lowest Sensitivity tested. Figure 3 shows that the bottom resolution degenerates as Sensitivity is decreased, but ALL the

Figure 3. Selection response due to changing sensitivity.

shoalest values are still selected. The loss of resolution comes at the expense of deeps and minor bottom detail being omitted.

Specified Sensitivity	0.5	1.0	2.0	5.0	10.0
Peak / Deep Selections	26	21	16	10	7
Total Selections	37	32	27	21	18

Table 1. Selection variation due to changing the Sensitivity

The second parameter that changes the size of the thresholds is the depth of the water for each sounding interval. This is an automatic factor that is not under the control of the operator. The effect is to reduce the number of selections in deeper water. Deeper depths were simulated by adding an offset to each actual sounding of the baseline data set. These results are summarized in table 2 and demonstrated by figure 4.

The additional selections ranged from 9 to 26 over the testing interval as the depth was artificially adjusted. The important result is that although the number of selections is reduced, the basic shape of the bottom profile has not significantly changed at the greatest depth tested.

Figure 4. Selection response due to changes in the sounded depth.

Added to the Actual Depth	0	+100	+500
Apparent Depth	20-120	120-220	520-620
Peak / Deep Additions	26	16	9
Total Selections	37	27	20

Table 2. Selection variation due to a changing bottom depth.

Figure 4 shows that bottom resolution degenerates slightly as depth increases, but ALL the shoalest and deepest values are still selected. The loss of resolution comes at the expense of minor bottom detail being omitted.

The phase shift is the possible difference of the start of a sounding interval with respect to a bottom feature. The start of a sounding line and hence the sounding interval beginning is completely random. For proper operation of the selection routine, the resulting bottom profile should be independent of phase. Ideally, every actual peak and deep should ALWAYS be selected regardless of the different intermediate depths selected. For testing purposes, four phase angles were compared: 0, 90, 180, and 270 degrees. These results are summarized in table 3 and demonstrated by figure 5. The additional selections varied between 32 and 37 for the different phase angles. The resulting bottom profiles remain essentially identical with only slight differences in areas of minor bottom detail.

Phase Angle (degrees)	0	90	180	270
Peak / Deep Additions	26	21	25	21
Total Selections	37	32	36	32

Table 3. Selection variation due to changing the Phase Angle.

The number of sounded depths within each sounding interval will not be fixed. The selection response for sounding intervals of 50 and 200 soundings per interval were compared to the baseline of 100 soundings. The additional peak and deep selections ranged from 22 to 37 over the baseline

Figure 5. Comparison of the bottom profile at different phase angles.

Figure 6. Selection response due to changing the interval size.

data set. Thus, the average number of extra selections per sounding interval is approximately three out of the maximum possible of eight additions. It is noted that an increased bottom detail resolution is obtained when the interval size is reduced, and the opposite effect occurs

when the interval size is increased. In the latter case, the basic shape of the bottom profile has not significantly degenerated. These results are summarized in table 4 and demonstrated by figure 6.

Interval Size	50	100	200
Peak / Deep Additions	37	26	22
Total Selections	58	37	28
Average Number of Additions per Interval	1.9	2.6	4.4

Table 4. Selection variation due to a changing sounding interval size.

The selections of four additional blocks of sounding data were compared using the baseline selection criteria. The first four blocks have nearly the same bottom irregularity, while the last is much more regular. As can be seen from these data, the number of additional selections is significantly effected by the bottom irregularity. This is as intended. The four irregular profiles averaged 2.4 additional selections, while the smoother bottom only resulted in 1.0 additional selection per interval. The comparison results are summarized in table 5.

Data Set	06	09	02	08	12
Peak / Deep Selections	26	19	27	26	10
Total Additions	37	31	38	38	21
Average Number of Additions per Interval	2.6	1.7	2.7	2.4	1.0

Table 5. Selection comparisons of different bottom sections.

4. COMPARISON WITH HYDROPLOT

The performance of the algorithm was compared to the selection results of the HYDROPLOT system. A sample of 39 NOS hydrographers, survey technicians, cartographic technicians and cartographers were surveyed in order to quantify the number of additional depths each would add

to the retained data set to "adequately" define the same five bottom profiles. The result of this survey is summarized in table 6 and demonstrated by figure 7. It is noted from these data that professional opinion as to what is significant and what is not varies greatly. Consistency of selection is seen as an advantage of the automated process. The distribution appears to be trimodal, grouping around 1, 4, and 10 added selections.

HYDROPLOT would have automatically selected and retained 11 soundings and the "average" hydrographer would have selected and manually entered an additional 5 soundings for the same data. If this relationship were typical of the entire survey area, then the total number of retained depths using the SDS III algorithm would be approximately 1.7 times more than the surveys presently acquired by using HYDROPLOT.

Data Set	06	09	02	08	12
Mean	4.5	2.8	4.5	6.3	1.6
Mode	4	3	2	5	0
Most Additions	11	9	14	16	8
Least Additions	0	0	0	1	0
Standard Deviation	2.6	1.9	3.5	2.7	2.1

Table 6. Additional hydrographer peak and deep selections for different bottom sections.

5. PROFILE ACCURACY

The collection of line segments connecting the retained soundings from a sounding line are a digital model of the bottom profile along that line. Two indices of the "goodness of fit" of the digital representation to the actual bottom are (1) the summation of all the depth differences between them and (2) the greatest single difference found between them. Both this Closeness Index and Maximum Error were determined for three situations using the baseline data set. The three cases are (1) the initial HYDROPLOT selections only, (2) these initial soundings plus the additions an "average" hydrographer would add to the HYDROPLOT selections, and (3) these initial soundings plus the automated selections with a Sensitivity of 2.0. The results of this comparison are summarized in table 7.

These data demonstrate the necessity to augment the HYDROPLOT initial selections with the most significant peak and deep soundings, in order to obtain a better bottom profile representation. The automated selection algorithm significantly improves the digital sounding line model generated by the "average" hydrographer and may vastly improve it with respect to some current surveys.

	HYDROPLOT INITIAL ONLY	WITH MANUAL ADDS	WITH AUTO ADDS
Total Soundings	11	16	27
Closeness Index	2495	1287	618
Total Improvement	---	48.4%	75.2%
Automated Improvement over Manual Adds	---	---	52.0%
Maximum Error (ft)	13.1	6.3	4.0
Total Error Reduction	---	51.9%	69.5%
Automated Reduction over Manual Adds	---	---	36.5%

Table 7. Improvements in the fixed interval bottom profile representation by adding manual or automatic selections.

6. SUMMARY

A computer-assisted sounding selection routine was developed for inclusion in the SDS III. A sounding selection algorithm was developed and tested using raw DSF-6000N sounding data. The significant peak and deep selections made by this algorithm were found to reduce the error between the actual bottom profile when compared to a profile reconstructed from selections made manually by NOS hydrographers. The inclusion of this automated processing routine will significantly improve the quality of the resulting digital bottom profile representation as well as the overall SDS III data processing efficiency.

Figure 7. Comparison between automated SDS III selections and HYDROPLOT fixed interval and manual additions.